

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN GEN-Z'S TOURISM DESTINATION SELECTION IN AN EMERGING NATION

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Abstract

Generation Z constitutes a substantial demography of social media (SM) users, serving as the vanguard in countries, particularly emerging nations such as Bangladesh. Their vacation destination choices are greatly shaped by SM, which offers more engaging and targeted communication compared to traditional methods. This study explores the Influence of SM on destination preferences among Gen Z in emerging economies. Data were collected from 334 Bangladeshi tourists through a structured questionnaire using judgmental sampling. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed for analysis. Results indicate significant positive relationships between Gen Z's destination decisions and three SM elements: online travel agents (OTA), social media content (SMC), and tourism and travel blogs (TTB). Specifically, OTA ($\beta = 0.606, p < 0.01$), SMC ($\beta = 0.203, p < 0.01$), and TTB ($\beta = 0.102, p < 0.01$) all showed strong, statistically significant influences on destination selection. These findings offer practical insights for travel service providers and tourism boards to refine digital marketing strategies to engage Gen Z travelers better.

Keywords: Gen-z, Destination selection, Social Media, Emerging Nation, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Generation Z, often called "digital natives," represents a tech-savvy cohort that heavily depends on digital platforms for everyday decisions (Werenowska & Rzepka, 2020). Gen Z exhibits a heightened dependency on mobile devices and internet-based information compared to previous generations, making them more selective and informed consumers (Figeac & Favre, 2023). About 3.48 billion individuals use SM, with 3.2 billion using mobile devices (Datareportal 2019). Their preference for short, visually appealing content and reliance on peer opinions via digital platforms

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distinguish them in decision-making behaviors, particularly in lifestyle-related domains like tourism. Moreover, Gen-Z, recognized for its heightened susceptibility to SM relative to other demographics, possesses smartphones and internet access, which enhance their ability to choose goods or services and render them more discerning and selective than preceding generations (Akın & Şener, 2023).

The growing Influence of social media (SM) has transformed how people plan and experience travel. With billions of active users globally, SM enables individuals to share travel content, seek reviews, and make destination decisions based on peer-generated information. According to De Souza and Costa Machado (2017), SM is a source of inspiration and a primary tool for validating travel options through user-generated content, influencers, and travel platforms.

Social networks have transformed communication, engagement, and the ability to generate and share information with others globally to the point where it is now an everyday event. More specifically, the constantly shifting SM landscape has presented the travel and tourism sector with "new potential" (Chu et al., 2020). SM exposes people all over the world to travel-related content regularly (Wang & Park, 2023). People are more likely to make well-informed judgments when supplied with relevant and well-reasoned information provided by SM (Shah & Asghar, 2023). This suggests a good likelihood that travel decisions, including those for hotels, destinations, and restaurants, are influenced by SM (Hysa et al., 2021).

Although numerous studies (e.g., Nur'afifah & Prihantoro, 2021; Werenowska & Rzepka, 2020; Zorlu & Candan 2023) have investigated the impact of SM on travel decisions, the majority have centered on millennials, often overlooking the unique behavioral patterns of Gen Z. Furthermore, most research either highlights SM influencers or destination image (e.g., Baber & Baber 2023; Gulati, 2024; Wang & Park, 2023) without critically assessing the integrated impact of online travel agents (OTA), social media content (SMC), and tourism blogs (TTB) from the Gen Z perspective.

This study aims to fill this gap by exploring how Gen Z in emerging nations utilizes SM to select travel destinations. It particularly focuses on the impact of OTA, SMC, and TTB on their decision-making process, contributing to a clearer understanding of how tourism marketing can be tailored for this digitally native group.

RQ1: How does Gen-Z select tourism destinations using social media in emerging nations?

RQ2: What specific types of social media content or platforms are most influential for Gen-Z in selecting tourism destinations in emerging nations?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Social Media

Based on Ghaly (2023), SM allows people to communicate with others at any time and place about their thoughts, views, and experiences. Social networking sites function as a unique subset of media tools with several properties in common, and they are more than just an interface with textual, audio, and visual affordances (Kent & Li, 2020). Moreover, it has various features and purposes, which are constantly

changing (Rhee et al., 2021). Tanković and Vidović (2023) describe at every stage of the decision-making process, SM can be used as a digital tool that emphasizes user-generated material or communication. It impacts the entire travel process, making communication, information collection, and decision-making easier. It is one of the most dependable information sources widely used at every trip planning stage (Liu et al., 2020).

In the age of SM, Social media influencers or SMI can still be shaped by actual travel. Still, they can also be jointly formed by individuals through exchanging and generating messages on SM platforms and by interacting with others through these (Huang et al., 2024). Tourism and travel agencies believe customers frequently search for trips, select their destinations, and share their experiences at a hostel, eatery, or airline through SM (Thuy et al., 2021). Applications like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, and Instagram are examples of SM, and they significantly impact how people behave regarding their destination selection (Majeed et al., 2020). On SM, views held by tourists regarding customer-generated content that is trustworthy and helpful on the Internet could have a good effect on their plans to use SM to plan a trip (Dedeoğlu et al., 2020).

2.2 Destination Selection

In tourism, 'Destination' is the primary environment and can be defined as a geographical region with specific boundaries and attractiveness that can attract tourists and meet their needs (Huang et al., 2023). Komilova et al. (2021) define a "tourist destination" as a particular location, address, home, or historical pilgrimage place visited by persons who do not stay there permanently and are not locals for tourism purposes. Destination competitiveness is the driving force behind tourist places' ability to draw tourists. (Bagchi & Uddin, 2021). Woyo (2023) defined tourist destination competitiveness as the capacity of the location to maximize its appeal to both locals and visitors and provide customers with innovative, high-quality, and appealing (and reasonably priced) tourism services.

Attractive destinations are key to tourism (Pandey & Joshi, 2021). So, the notion of "DS" mainly concentrates on the elements and procedures that impact travellers' decisions on where to go on vacation (Chu et al., 2022). The choice of destination comprises a set of complex and multidimensional processes (Bire et al., 2021). Accessibility, health and hygiene, and experience work as motivators for any DS (Nair & Sinha, 2020). Some researchers identified factors like destination attractions, image, cost, amenities, accessibility, and location attractiveness that shape travelers' DS choices (Seyidov & Adomaitienė, 2016). Terminus's image and its attraction are crucial in selecting a spot (Khongrat, 2024). Because of technological advances, SMCs like short videos on destinations and food blogs provide richer information than text or images, which also helps to make travel choices (Li et al., 2020). So, as believed by Paul et al. (2019), SM provides information and serves as a suggestion for DS.

While visiting international tourist spots, factors like 'Destination Image & Attractions', 'Destination Climate', 'Destination Credibility', and 'Recreational Facilities' affect destination selection (Baena & Cerviño, 2024). On the other hand,

some researchers identified that decisions on tourist location depend on experiential, service, and cultural factors like local cuisine, food satisfaction, and hospitality services, especially in India (Ghaderi et al., 2024). A study by Salamzadeh et al. (2022) identified that in developed countries like Poland, China, and many more, Individuals frequently use SM apps and new technology to influence how they see and select their destination. They base their decision-making on their knowledge of the benefits and drawbacks of these journeys (Salamzadeh et al., 2022). Content made by user approaches through SM like TikTok, and Instagram influences tourist's social environment and destination selection in Indonesia (Nur'afifah & Prihantoro, 2021).

However, in developing countries like Bangladesh, people mostly rely on natural beauty, destination attractions, accessibility, amenities, reference groups, etc. To make their travel choice (Mim et al., 2022). However, pull factors like family and social effects also impact the decision-making process of the destination (Dahiya & Batra 2016). Karim et al. (2024) identified that positive word of mouth and destination satisfaction encourage tourists visiting Bangladesh.

2.3 Gen Z in the Emerging Nation

Individuals born after 1995 are known as Gen Z and are proficient in SM and technology (Chang et al., 2023). According to Munifah et al. (2024), Gen Z is known for its self-centeredness as they are young, independent, and used to the latest information and communication technology developments. Besides, they have a strong awareness and understanding of environmental concerns (Dragolea et al., 2023). They can use SM because they are highly familiar with technology (Toma & Hudea, 2024). They (ages 16 to 36) are seen as a significant demographic, especially in SM use like Instagram and TikTok, as well as entertainment platforms like Netflix (Tirocchi et al., 2024).

Previous studies on Gen Z destination selection suggest various factors like individual trips, accommodation, performance expectancy, social influences, economic and personal aspects, etc. (Daskin et al., 2024). Others found that individuals' norms, values, preferences, and thought patterns influence DS, according to Gen Z (Octaviany & Mardiyana, 2024). With the changes in time, some researchers identified SMC, including information, video, and text, as helping to shape destination image and influence Gen-Z tourism preferences (Wang & Park, 2023; Pitanatri et al., 2024). Moreover, the attitude, experiences, and user-produced content information reliability shared by SMI also affect their DS (Pitanatri et al., 2024; Ghaly, 2023).

Research on Gen Z in a developing country like India revealed common traits, including ongoing education, professional development and progress, independence, increased adaptability, work-life balance, and a thorough comprehension of the organization's principles, vision, and strategic objectives (Chillakuri 2020). Gen Z is a noteworthy subject for any industry to analyze and find the pattern of their decision-making. According to Mahapatra et al. (2022), Gen Z of developing nations tends to be determined by technology, and the available information on the Internet can shape decisions.

Regarding generational disparities, Prayag et al. (2022) state that while there are variations within Gen Z, there are differences between Gen Z tourists and Baby Boomers, Y and X, regarding their travel habits and views toward the environment. He added that compared to previous generations, Gen Z travelers still use public transportation, bicycles, and electric automobiles at a relatively low rate, despite their greater emphasis on resource conservation, community-building activities, purchasing locally grown food, and using eco-friendly products. Accordingly, Qiu et al. (2022) demonstrate that Gen Z has substantially lower behavioral intentions related to environmental responsibility, particularly concerning environmental protection concerns, social interaction, reporting damage, recycling garbage, etc. To conclude, current studies on Gen Z and their tourism-related decisions have yielded different results that demand more research.

Technology plays a significant role in developing sustainable tourism preferences and destination selection by Gen Z, like Porto (Sfodera et al., 2024). With the help of technology, SM also influences the DS of young people in developing countries like China, Vietnam, Oman, etc. (Zhou et al., 2023; Daskin & Tumati, 2024). In Bangladesh, the establishment's natural beauty, safety and security, accommodation, transportation, communication system, budget and time, local cuisine, and attitude of local people affect Gen Z DS (Sojib et al., 2023). Mim et al. (2022) identified that reference groups, SM, safety and security, and destination image affect traveler decisions in Bangladesh. Regarding Community-based tourism, Gen Z also has an influential role in making decisions and inspiring traveling (Amin et al., 2024).

3. Hypothesis Development

Table 1: List of Hypotheses

SN	Hypothesis
H_1	<i>SM's tourism and travel blog has positive implications for the DS of Gen Z.</i>
H_2	<i>The use of SM through mobile applications has positive implications for Gen Z's DS.</i>
H_3	<i>The content of SM has positive implications for the DS of Gen Z.</i>
H_4	<i>SMI has a favourable implication on the DS of Gen Z</i>
H_5	<i>Online travel agent (OTA) has a positive implication on the DS of Gen Z</i>

3.1 Tourism and travel blog

Halkiopoulous et al. (2023) state that travel blogs and tourism constitute a digital marketing channel. This digital transformation in tourism is based on sophisticated online applications that streamline travel for travelers and confer benefits to the entire tourism sector regarding communication and related transactions (Firican, 2023). According to Chen et al. (2019), videos, particularly blogs by other travelers, can influence users' desire to travel. According to Chauhan (2023), it promotes tourism destinations and sites of interest using electronic media and communication technologies, such as SM platforms and websites. Only one travel agency uses

mobile phone marketing to run its business; all other travel companies rely solely on a few electronic websites and SM platforms (Briez et al., 2021).

H₁: The tourism and travel blog of SM has positive implications for the DS of Gen Z.

3.2 Mobile Applications

SM consists of different ways, such as websites, MA, networks, etc. MA, however, is one of the best mediums for accessing SM because of how easy and accessible it is to the customers (Velappan & Karmenivannan, 2024). According to Statista (2021), Facebook has the most monthly active users, about 2.9 billion, followed by YouTube with 2.2 billion, and WhatsApp with 2.0 billion; these platforms undoubtedly have the most impactful Influence in the present trend regardless of the product and services. Research by the Media Post has discovered that 48% of Instagram consumers rely on videos and pictures to make travel decisions, and 35% utilize them to research new places and explore unique destinations (Velappan & Karmenivannan, 2024). According to Trivedi et al. (2021), all SM applications influence the thinking process of their users' brains to make decisions and spend more time on them.

H₂: The use of SM through mobile applications has positive implications for the DS of Gen Z.

3.3 Social Media Content

According to Park et al. (2018), Social Media content or SMC is a valuable source of information for destination marketers and travelers, as it offers a wealth of up-to-date travel-related information together with realistic and vivid perspectives from other travelers' stories. SM is still crucial to the tourism industry in several ways (Alghizzawi et al., 2018). Different content kinds can influence visitors' DS intentions, according to research, since textual material can alter visitors' emotions depending on how long it is, and this can, therefore, impact visitors' DS and visit intents (Bufquin et al., 2020). The significance of textual SMC in reflecting visitors' reactions and feelings in response to contextual circumstances was also highlighted (Pachucki & Scholl-Grissmann, 2022). According to Zhang et al. (2020), user-generated material from visitors and locals provides crucial information that shapes a destination's overall perception and affects visitors' behavioral preferences. (Trivedi et al., 2021)

H₃: The content of SM has positive implications for the DS of Gen Z.

3.4 Social Media Influencers

In this modern era, social media influencers (SMIs) are known as influential figures and brand promoters on SM platforms (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020). According to Schouten et al. (2020), partnering with SMI is more efficient than conventional celebrities. Besides, marketers utilize 93% of their campaign activities through SMI, and 66% of them are projecting to increase their influencer marketing investment (Belanche et al., 2021). Furthermore, Influencers are considered a great communication tool to create a place in customers' minds (Djafarova & Bowes 2021). As per De Veirman (2017), followers rely on influencer's advice for their experience in particular topics. Current research has found the effectiveness of

sponsorship encouraging a product/service to the customers (Boerman, 2020). In addition, most studies found that sponsorship programs directly motivate customers to make decisions (Reinikainen et al., 2020). As specified by Danes and Duthler (2019), the achievements of SMI depend on their followers. SMI specializes in different subjects relating to the follower's interest in that particular topic, which creates a distinctive place in the customer's mind (Zhang et al., 2020).

H4: SMI has a positive implication on the DS of Gen Z.

3.5 Online Travel Agent

As information about tourist sites and attractions is readily available, travel tastes changed from luxury demands to basic needs (Kazoba et al., 2016). Communication, information, and technology are growing more rapidly to meet people's need for quick and precise information. Like the tourism industry, fast and accurate information is required to facilitate travelers' access to the destination. (Kazoba et al., 2016).

H5: Online travel agent has a positive implication on the DS of Gen Z.

3.6 Association between the SM factors and DS

Many studies have focused on measuring destination image and what motivates consumers to look for different travel options (Wei et al., 2022). According to Zhang et al. (2020), videos, particularly vlogs by other travelers, can influence users' desire to travel. Furthermore, few studies have examined the connection between domestic travelers' intention to return to a place and their perception of trust. (Hassan & Soliman, 2021). MA can be a driver for revisiting intentions and influencing the buying choices of tourists concerning their preferences. There is a need to research the motives of travelers. Several studies conducted on MA suggest that understanding travel motives is central to destination expansion and growth (Bayih and Singh, 2020). Different content types can influence visitors' DS intentions (Bufquin et al., 2020).

4. Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of dependent and independent variables

5. Objectives of the Study

The key objective of this investigation is to examine the connections between Gen-Z and destination selection via the usage of SM platforms.

5.1 Specific Objectives

- To discover the critical driving factors of SM to transform the intention into DS.
- To evaluate the impact of visitors' awareness of the tourism and travel blog, Mobile application, SMC, SMI, and OTA for DS by Gen Z.
- To examine tourists' perceptions of SM and Gen Z's purpose in selecting their destinations.

6. Research Methodology

Research methodology is the section that describes the steps followed in the execution of the study as well as a brief description of the research method used (Sobh & Perry, 2006). SM plays a significant role in selecting a tourist destination. This study adopted a quantitative research approach to ascertain the Influence of SM on tourists' DS by Gen Z.

6.1 Research Design

A survey method using a quantitative research approach was applied to evaluate Gen Z's perceptions regarding SM's performance in DS. In this study, the non-probability sampling method called judgmental sampling has been used to comprehend and express its objective.

6.2 Population, Sample Frame, and Sample Size

The research sample consists of people who were born between 1997 and 2009. A representative sample consisting of people in different areas, like offices, universities, colleges, and other institutions, etc., has been studied. Judgmental sampling processes were used as a sampling approach because of the inherent volatility and unpredictability of the entire population. Hair et al. (2010) state that for the majority of multivariate analyses, such as regression and SEM, a sample size greater than 200 is deemed sufficient. Furthermore, Amin et al. (2024) used 201 samples to measure the divergence of alternative tourism in emerging nations. Considering resource limitations, pilot study findings, and previous literature related to tourism, the study used 334 respondents as the sample size.

6.3 Data collection

A structured questionnaire was constructed to collect primary data. The survey included 33 questions considering six independent variables: TTB, Mobile application, SMC, SMI, OTA, and one dependent variable: DS. A hybrid technique was used to conduct the survey.

6.4 Data Analysis Technique and Measurement of Reliability and Validity

The study adopted PLS-SEM tools to comprehend the driving effect of SM on selecting tourist destinations from a Gen Z perspective. Validity means evaluating the caliber of the research design and methodologies selected (Collis & Hussey, 2014). The study conducted a pilot survey to examine the questionnaire's validity. Cronbach's alpha was also evaluated to assess the reliability of the study. Items with a Cronbach's alpha value of more than 0.70 are thought to have better internal consistency (Nunnally, 1978).

6.5 Research Instrument

Measurement and scaling methods have been used to quantify the research variables. The structured questionnaire was divided into two sections. Focusing on demographic information, this section comprises three questions. The second section contains 33 questions focusing on variables like TTB, mobile application, SMC, SMI, OTA, and DS. A five-point Likert scale has been used for scaling each item, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The description of the measurement instruments is given below:

Table 2: Items of the Variables

Serial	IVs	Serial	Items	Source
1	Tourism and travel blog	i.	Communication	Firican, (2023);
		ii.	Desire to travel	Chen et al. (2019)
		iii.	Promotion of sites	Chauhan (2023)
		iv.	Companies' reliability	Briez et al., (2021)
		v.	Digital tourism marketing channel	Halkiopoulos et al. (2023)
2	Mobile Applications	i.	Facebook	Velappan & Karmenivannan, (2024); Trivedi et al. (2021)
		ii.	Instagram	
		iii.	Pinterest	
		iv.	WhatsApp	
		v	X	
3	Social Media Content	i.	Sources of information	Park et al. (2018)
		ii.	Crucial media	Alghizzawi et al. (2018)
		iii.	Decision of Destination	Bufquin et al. (2020),

		iv.	Reaction and Feelings	Pachucki & Scholl-Grisseemann (2022) ,
		v.	Overall perception	Zhang et al. (2020)
4	Social Media Influencers	i.	Campaign	De Veirman et al., (2020)
		ii.	Influencer Advice	
		iii.	Sponsorship	Boerman, (2020);
		iv.	Relationship with followers	Dhanesh & Duthler, (2019)
5	Online Travel Agent	i.	Accessibility of information regarding tourists' destinations	Kazoba & Massaw (2016)
		ii.	Fast information provider	Untari & Satria, (2019);
		iii.	Accurate information provider	
		iv.	Traveler's services provider	
6	Destination Selection	i.	Destination Image	Seyidov & Admaitiene, (2016); Khongrat, (2024);
		ii.	Experience	
		iii.	Location attraction	
		iv.	Local cuisine	
		v.	Destination safety	

Source: Authors Calculation

6.6 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Details of participating respondents are shown below:

Table 3: Demographic profile of the respondents (n = 334)

Characteristics		Percent
Gender	Male	54.19%
	Female	45.81%

Age	Under 15	0.3%
	15-18	3.29%
	19-22	19.76%
	23-26	75.45%
	27-30	1.20%
	Over 30	0%

Source: Authors Calculation

Table iii represents the outcomes of the circumstantial characteristics of the respondents. According to the results, the male respondents represented about 54.19%, whereas 45.81% were female respondents. The table also shows that the maximum of the respondents was aged between 23 and 26, which accounts for 75.45% of the total respondents; also, 19.76% were from 19-22, 3.29% were from 15-18, 1.20% were from 27-30, 0.3% were from Under 15, and 0% were from Over 30. The respondents were students and professionals from Gen Z from different schools, colleges, universities, and offices.

7. Data Analysis and Interpretation

7.1 Measurement Model

The outer model test classifies validity and reliability tests for PLS-SEM. An outer model analysis shows how each indicator is related to its latent variables. In this work, outer model testing evaluates convergent validity, discriminant validity, AVE, and reliability using composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha (Table iv). To examine convergent validity, the loading factor values for each construct should be more than 0.7. (Hair et al., 2014). However, values between .60 and .70 can be justified for significant constructs (Hair et al., 2019). The loading values in this investigation ranged from 0.675 to 0.984. Hair et al. (2014) recommended that the threshold for two reliability measures, α and ρ_A , be 0.700 and higher. Table iv shows that the α and ρ_A values are above the threshold, and the results show that all constructs have reliability ratings over 0.700, indicating that they exceed the limit values for α and ρ_A . The convergent validity test also evaluates the AVE, which must be > 0.500 , the average value of the squared loadings of the items associated with the construct; the AVE values for TTB, MA, SMI, SMC, OTA, and DS, respectively, are 0.672, 0.687, 0.747, 0.856, 0.966 and 0.619.

Table 4: Factor loading, reliability, and AVE outcomes

Construct	Factor Loading	M	SD	Cronbach's α	Composite Reliability	AVE
<i>Tourism and Travel Blogs (TTB)</i>				0.879	0.911	0.672
TTB1	0.745	0.740	0.046			
TTB2	0.847	0.845	0.028			

TTB3	0.825	0.822	0.030			
TTB4	0.854	0.855	0.022			
TTB5	0.823	0.822	0.028			
Mobile Application (MA)						
MA1	0.858	0.841	0.100	0.887	0.916	0.687
MA2	0.877	0.860	0.097			
MA3	0.828	0.807	0.088			
MA4	0.815	0.806	0.077			
MA5	0.761	0.752	0.09			
Social Media Influencers (SMI)						
SMI1	0.870	0.864	0.051	0.890	0.922	0.747
SMI2	0.823	0.812	0.056			
SMI3	0.910	0.908	0.046			
SMI4	0.852	0.840	0.052			
Social Media Content (SMC)						
SMC1	0.937	0.936	0.008	0.958	0.967	0.856
SMC2	0.950	0.949	0.007			
SMC3	0.940	0.940	0.009			
SMC4	0.894	0.894	0.014			
SMC5	0.903	0.904	0.012			
Online Travel Agent (OTA)						
OTA2	0.982	0.982	0.004	0.965	0.967	0.966
OTA4	0.984	0.984	0.003			
Destination Selection (DS)						
DS1	0.853	0.852	0.019	0.845	0.890	0.619
DS2	0.818	0.819	0.023			
DS3	0.813	0.813	0.022			
DS4	0.763	0.761	0.030			
DS5	0.675	0.676	0.048			

Source: Author's calculation based on survey data

A discriminant validity test guarantees each construct's uniqueness and distinction from the other constructs being studied. The discriminant validity was assessed using the HTMT and the Fornell-Larker Criteria (In Tables v and vi). As part of the

discriminant validity test, the square root of the AVE was compared to the link of latent variables; the AVE has a more substantial correlation value than the other constructs, supporting the threshold (Hair et al., 2014). Therefore, the discriminant validity of the TTB, MA, SMI, SMC, OTA, and DS constructs is excellent. Furthermore, as all HTMT values are less than 0.850, the HTMT ratio results prove that the constructs have excellent discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 5: Discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Construct	AVE	Fornell-Larcker Criterion					
		DS	MA	OTA	SMC	SMI	TTB
DS	0.619	0.787					
MA	0.687	-0.16	0.829				
OTA	0.966	0.743	-0.269	0.983			
SMC	0.856	0.575	-0.239	0.629	0.925		
SMI	0.747	-0.169	0.163	-0.236	-0.373	0.864	
TTB	0.672	0.278	-0.049	0.252	0.082	0.285	0.82

Source: Author's calculation based on survey data

Table 6: Discriminant validity (HTMT analysis)

Connecting Variables	HTMT
MA -> DS	0.185
OTA -> DS	0.817
SMC -> DS	0.632
SMI -> DS	0.194
TTB -> DS	0.306

Source: Author's calculation based on survey data

7.2 Structural Model

The VIF, R², and path coefficient values—obtained using PLS and shown in Tables vii and viii—are crucial to structural model analyses. VIF values determine the lack of significant collinearity, test for multicollinearity, and create relationships between exogenous variables. According to Hair et al. (2014), Table vii demonstrates that the VIF values are below the crucial value of 3.00. Consequently, multicollinearity is not present in the suggested constructs.

Table 7: Collinearity test

Connecting Variables	VIF
MA -> DS	1.095 <3.00
OTA -> DS	1.844 <3.00
SMC -> DS	1.822 <3.00
SMI -> DS	1.339 <3.00
TTB -> DS	1.245 <3.00

Source: Author's calculation based on survey data

The determinant coefficient test, which ranges from 0 to 1, evaluates how accurately the model predicts outcomes by considering the combined impact of exogenous and endogenous variables. According to Hair et al. (2014), this study models predicted accuracy increases with value. While OS is exogenous, TTB, MA, SMI, SMC, and OTA are endogenous variables. Table viii displays the estimated R-square values, showing that the value exceeds the .50 threshold.

Table 8: Coefficient determinant test

Variables	R-square
DS	0.584

Source: Author's calculation based on survey data

As shown in Table ix, hypotheses were tested using the path coefficient value to ascertain the relationship between the variables being studied. H1 determines whether TTB and DS are positively correlated. The findings indicated that TTB significantly affects DS ($\beta = 0.102$, $t = 2.409$, $p = 0.016$). H1 is supported as a result. H2 concludes that MA has a negligible effect on DS ($\beta = 0.055$, $t = 1.437$, $p = 0.151$). H2 is thus not supported. H3 hence concludes that SMC affects DS ($\beta = 0.203$, $t = 3.87$, $p = 0.000$). Consequently, H3 is also proven. H4 consequently concludes that SMI has no substantial effects on DS ($\beta = 0.012$, $t = 0.283$, $p = 0.777$). H4 is thus not supported. OTA positively correlates with DS, according to H5 ($\beta = 0.606$, $t = 12.447$, $p = 0.000$). H5 is supported as a result.

Table 9: Direct relationship analysis

Hypotheses	Path	β	STDEV	t	p	Results
H ₁	TTB -> DS	0.102	0.042	2.409	0.016	Supported
H ₂	MA -> DS	0.055	0.038	1.437	0.151	Not supported
H ₃	SMC -> DS	0.203	0.052	3.87	0	Supported
H ₄	SMI ->DS	0.012	0.042	0.283	0.777	Not supported
H ₅	OTA -> DS	0.606	0.049	12.447	0	Supported

Source: Author's calculation based on survey data

Figure 2: Research Model

8. Discussion on Findings

8.1 Key Findings and Implications

This study examined how the implications of SM can impact the long-term viability of DS in the tourism industry. The findings confirm that Online Travel Agents (OTA), Social Media Content (SMC), and Tourism and Travel Blogs (TTB) exhibit strong and statistically significant positive relationships with Gen Z's destination choices. This suggests that Gen Z does not merely consume digital content passively but actively engages with these sources when making travel decisions.

A possible reason for this pattern is that Gen Z spends significant time on social media platforms. They trust peer reviews, influencer recommendations, and visual storytelling in travel content, which stimulates interest and emotional connection to destinations. For this generation, digital content's quality, creativity, and authenticity play a more important role than traditional advertisements.

8.2 Comparison with Previous Literature

The findings support and extend prior research by Zhou et al. (2023) and Cheng et al. (2024), who found that SM content and online platforms strongly influence travel planning. However, this study provides a more focused lens on Gen Z, which often merges with millennials in broader studies.

While previous studies have acknowledged the role of SM, this research highlights that TTB and OTA platforms, often overlooked in favor of influencer marketing, also significantly shape Gen Z behavior. This distinction is essential for travel marketers seeking a more comprehensive digital strategy.

8.3 Practical and Policy Implications

As of April 2024, Bangladesh had approximately 66 million Facebook users, with over 50% aged 18–24, reflecting the dominance of Gen Z in the digital space (Datareportal, 2024). The growing tourism demand, supported by government initiatives in eco-tourism and heritage promotion, requires a strategic use of digital channels.

Tourism marketers and policymakers should invest in high-quality, interactive SMC, develop OTA platforms with better UX and personalized suggestions, and collaborate with TTB writers to enhance destination visibility to optimise the impact on Gen Z. Strengthening these channels will not only influence travel decisions but also contribute to sustainable growth in tourism. With a particular emphasis on eco-tourism, heritage sites, and community-based tourism in lesser-known locations, the government needs to take action to expand the range of tourism alternatives. Though there are infrastructural limitations due to the use of digital media and websites, the exposure is increasing day by day. To influence the new visitors' decision on a destination, there is a need for better SMC, OTA, and TTB.

8.4 Limitations and Future Research Directions

Future research could explore other influencing factors such as influencer credibility, digital literacy, online reviews, or peer pressure within SM communities. Moreover, using a judgmental sampling method and a cross-sectional design may limit the generalizability of the findings. Longitudinal or mixed-method studies could provide deeper insights into behavioral changes over time.

Lastly, more qualitative exploration, such as interviews or focus groups with Gen Z travelers, could enrich the understanding of the emotional and cognitive processes behind their decisions. Incorporating this qualitative dimension would allow researchers to interpret how trust, novelty-seeking, and social validation mediate the relationship between SM and destination selection.

9. Conclusion and Future Directions

In conclusion, SM has a remarkable influence on tourists' DS from the vantage point of Gen Z. The focus of the study was to find the role of SM in shaping tourism destination choices and which forms of SM platforms have the greatest impact on Gen Z in emerging nations. To select a destination, tourists must undergo several perceptions, preferences, and experiences. OTAs, SMCs, and experiences play crucial roles in selecting a destination. With the rapid expansion of SM usage, SM platforms allow travelers to share their thoughts and experiences and highlight destinations, creating aspirational images that influence potential visitors. This dynamic enhances a destination's visibility and attractiveness, which motivates people to select and visit a tourist spot. On the contrary, SM also poses challenges

such as oversaturation and the risk of promoting unrealistic expectations of tourists through SMC, affecting SM's trustworthiness and reliability. As Gen Z emerges as a significant consumer group that relies on SM for DS, it will be critical for the tourism industry to overcome the pitfalls of SM, aiming to attract and retain their interest. However, explicit, informative, and trustworthy content on reliable websites can make that happen. Additionally, the development of destination infrastructure and security can also enhance the image of a destination, which motivates the tourist's SM marketing, which is also crucial. Future research could further explore the growing trends in SM usage and their long-term effects on travel behavior.

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